

40° CONVEGNO NAZIONALE

AIDEA 2023

5-6 OTTOBRE - SALERNO

5/6
Ottobre
2023

Abstract conference proceeding

XL CONVEGNO NAZIONALE L'AZIENDALISMO CREA VALORE!

IL RUOLO DELL' ACCADEMIA NELLE SFIDE DELLA SOCIETÀ, DELL'ECONOMIA E DELLE ISTITUZIONI.

Dipartimento di Scienze Aziendali
Management & Innovation Systems
Università degli Studi di Salerno

ISBN: 978-88-947839-2-6

Scafati e Cetara
fondata nel 1914

BANCA ASSOCIATA AL
Gruppo Bancario Cooperativo Iccrea

Ordine dei Dottori Commercialisti
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Provincia di Salerno

ORDINE DEI
DOTTORI COMMERCIALISTI E
DEGLI ESPERTI CONTABILI DI
SALERNO

CEDAM

Lettera del presidente

Ogni comunità scientifica, con le proprie specificità, crea valore per la società. Nondimeno, noi aziendalisti esaltiamo tale contributo per il ruolo svolto nel processo formativo delle nuove generazioni e nella crescita e nello sviluppo dell'impresa.

Infatti, i nostri insegnamenti coinvolgono oltre il 10% degli studenti universitari italiani, a riprova dell'interesse delle nostre discipline e della nostra capacità di coinvolgimento.

Il rapporto osmotico con le imprese, contemporaneamente, ci induce a innovare continuamente i nostri contenuti didattici e a rafforzare la cultura d'impresa.

La varietà di contributi presentati in questo convegno evidenzia l'ampiezza dei nostri confini scientifici e la prevalente interdisciplinarietà conferma il superamento di antichi steccati, senza tuttavia stravolgere l'autonomia dei singoli settori scientifici.

Presentazione del convegno

La comunità scientifica avverte sempre più la necessità di un dialogo e di una visione interdipendente, trasversale e circolare tra i saperi economico-aziendali che, pur nelle loro specificità, ricevono afflato dall'unitaria e ancora attuale matrice da cui gli studiosi italiani traggono comune origine.

Per tali ragioni AIDEA, ancor più rispetto ai precedenti convegni che risalgono al periodo antecedente la pandemia da Covid-19 (l'edizione precedente, l'ultima in presenza, si è svolta a Torino nel 2019), ritiene possa essere estremamente importante accrescere la dialettica e la condivisione di percorsi di sviluppo dei saperi presenti nelle diverse anime dell'aziendalismo in relazione ai suoi principali stakeholder di riferimento.

AIDEA, con il suo convegno, vuole proiettarsi nel futuro con raccomandazioni che si augura siano utili per tutti coloro che, a vario titolo, studiano e si interfacciano con le discipline aziendali.

In questo modo, si vuole contribuire a sostenere la percezione delle nostre discipline e della conoscenza che gli studiosi sono in grado di generare, incoraggiando l'evoluzione e l'innovazione nelle ricerche e al tempo stesso interrogandosi criticamente sul nostro ruolo di accademici nella società civile.

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Does tourism policy planning impact the sustainability of tourist flows?

Evidence from Florence, Italy.

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the unsustainability of mass tourism, as there is no guarantee of social distance between people, and it can be a health risk. Moreover, the excessive level of tourism flows raises important questions with respect to environmental damage and impact on local population (Liberatore et al., 2022; Salerno et al., 2013). The uncontrolled development of tourism risks irreparably compromising the environmental, cultural, and social resources of a destination with consequences not only for the quality of life of residents but also for the local flora and fauna (Simon et al., 2004; Larson & Poudyal, 2012; Neuts & Nijkamp, 2012). Furthermore, tourist overcrowding poses a potential threat to the physical integrity of world heritage sites, as sustained influxes of tourists inevitably result in the "consumption" of the sites they visit, even if the visitors themselves demonstrate respect towards these places.

In Italy, cities as Florence, Venice and Rome, despite being recognized as the most popular destinations worldwide, confront the detrimental consequences of tourist congestion. These consequences are predominantly influenced by factors such as the sheer number of visitors in relation to the limited dimensions of their historic centres, the concentration of

historical and artistic treasures within these central areas, and the emergence of dysfunctional tourist behaviours. In addition to that, the phenomenon of overtourism has triggered intolerance among the local population in several tourist destinations around the world (WTTC & McKinsey, 2017; Tokarchuk, Gabriele, and Maurer, 2020).

Given the close relationship between tourism and the surrounding environment, local stakeholders need to focus on sustainability to preserve the tourist destination competitiveness and to control tourism flows (Urtasun & Gutiérrez, 2006; Larson & Poudyal, 2012).

The concept of sustainable development has been applied to tourism since the 1990s (Navarro et al., 2012). The aim is to establish planning, development, and management of tourism activities to mitigate the environment and socio-cultural impact of high visitor flows on host regions and communities as well as the detrimental effect on the tourism experience itself (McCool & Lime, 2001; Saarinen, 2006; UNWTO, 2018). Decision makers have been forced to adopt exceptional protective measures focus on regulating tourist flows and behaviour, limiting numbers, involving residents, or increasing environmental awareness (UNWTO, 2018). For example, to offset the constant influx of visitors, the city of Venice has decided to introduce a tourist entrance fee valid for 11 months out of 12, namely the period considered high season. In Barcelona, residents have made several protests and petitions against visitor and new visitors dwelling, demanding that tourism be managed in a more sustainable way. While Amsterdam's residents are only 14 percent, and local governments have begun promoting other cities near Amsterdam to decongest tourist flows.

The implementation of sustainability policies aimed at achieving a harmonious equilibrium between the experiential requirements of tourists and the liveability of the local population appears to be the sole solution in response to the gradual onset of stagnation and decline phases observed in numerous global destinations. However, ensuring the sustainability of tourism entails more than simply controlling and managing the pressures exerted by tourism

activities and their resulting impacts. It also necessitates the establishment of a novel framework for tourism development.

For this purpose, we believe that it is fundamental to examine factors that can prevent the negative effects linked to excessive levels of tourist flows instead of measuring the damages brought on by overtourism. In fact, at the heart of each action taken there is the necessity to assess the degree to which the problem is mitigated.

In this study, we decided to focus on policy planning as a possible solution for the problem of overtourism and unsustainability of tourism flows. Specifically, our purpose is to measure the effectiveness of policy planning in managing the impact of tourism flows in the city of Florence.

1. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Tourism is a factor of change of territorial systems (Saveriades, 2000; Saarinen, 2006) and its impetuous growth has attracted attention of experts and academics to investigate how tourism is affecting destinations and sites. In the last decades, concerns have been raised about the social and physical effects of tourism, along with an understanding of how it contributes to the well-being of local communities (McCool & Lime, 2001; Simon et al., 2004). On the one hand, tourism serves as an important force to develop the destination by creating jobs and new economic activities (Saveriades, 2000; Larson & Poudyal, 2012; Lobo et al., 2013). On the other hand, it raises important questions with respect to environmental damage, the changes to the social structure and the consumption of a site (Job et al., 2017; Liberatore et al., 2022; Salerno et al., 2013).

Many European destinations suffer from tourism overcrowding and this requires the local authorities to manage not only the tourist flows but also increasing discontent among the residents (Neuts and Nijkamp, 2012; Tokarchuk et al., 2020). Barcelona, Amsterdam, Florence and Venice are the cities that suffer the most from mass tourism and local managers have been

forced to intervene to reduce the phenomenon of overtourism and to focus on sustainability to preserve the tourist destination competitiveness (Urtasun & Gutiérrez, 2006; Larson & Poudyal, 2012).

Prior literature tried to measure the tourism sustainability developing a system of indicators able to assess the carrying capacity of a tourist destination in urban areas. Liberatore et al. (2022) utilised a dashboard to summarise the impact of overcrowding in historic centres of art cities and to support policy makers interventions. Similarly, the World Travel & Tourism Council and McKinsey (2017) have developed a toolkit for specific support for the decision-making process to help the urban destination administrations to develop an approach to manage tourism pressure with the active involvement of the local public and private stakeholders. Specifically, they developed an analytical tool based on nine indicators belonging to five macro-categories (alienation of local residents, degraded tourist experience; over-loaded infrastructure; damage to nature, and threats to cultural heritage) for defining the potential level of risk to a city.

Measuring the tourism pressure through a system of standardised indicators has been therefore envisioned as a strategic tool for facilitating the monitoring and control of the evolving tourism phenomenon in the historic centres of cities of art. In this sense, indicators offer a useful starting point to understand when it is necessary to intervene and review tourism management policies.

1.2 Regulation

As mentioned before, an effective way to preserve world heritage is to promote sustainable tourism (Bošković et al., 2020; Job et al., 2017). The latter can be a result of many initiatives, such as the sensibilization of tour operators (Goldberg et al., 2018) or as tourism planning (Ji et al., 2023; Job et al., 2017). In this context, local government tourist management may significantly reduce the impact of overtourism (García-Buades et al., 2022;

Thanvisitthpon, 2016) and create a balance between heritage protection and economic growth related to tourism (Wells et al., 2016). The World Heritage Committee suggested guidelines for tourism flow planning, promoting the regulation of tourist flows as a key element of sustainable tourism management (UNESCO; 2012; King and Halpenny, 2014).

Regulation makes possible to review tourism flow management policies, identify problems that need to be addressed by destination managers, and avoid tourist overcrowding in specific areas. The aim of the regulation is to provide visitors with timely information and rules to make them more aware of their responsibilities towards the environment, the local population and the host community. In addition, the risks of overcrowding should come into tourist awareness in order to affect their behaviour during the period of stay.

By regulating the opening hours of tourist attractions, the number of visitors allowed, or establishing areas with limited vehicular traffic by increasing pedestrian areas, it makes it possible to congest tourist flows around specific areas or attractions and protect the quality of life of residents as well as make the city more liveable and sustainable.

Cities have several options to deal with tourism related issues; one approach is to limit and/or exclude human use of a destination (Job, 2014; Serenari et al., 2017). Alternatively, “community-based” approaches such as the development of tourism strategies and policies to facilitate economic development of tourism related activities (Dinica, 2017).

As highlighted by previous literature, cities usually resort to policy interventions as the last attempt to keep the sustainability of tourism under control. A perfect example of this phenomenon is the tourism planning carried out in the management plan for the city; in this document destination managers try to assess the main critical issue for the city, usually referring also to excessive levels of tourism flows (for cities that suffer from overtourism) and to tourism management strategies (Calle-Vaquero et al., 2021; Job et al., 2017).

A few examples of this phenomenon are the municipal strategies for public space management in the city of Amsterdam (Pourbahador and Brinkhuijsen, 2023), the strategic planning in the World Heritage Sites (Job et al., 2017), the regulation of short-term rentals (Nieuwland and Van Melik, 2020; Van Holm, 2020), and the licensing systems employed in specific fields ad whale shark tourism (Catlin et al., 2012).

1.3 Research objectives and hypotheses development

What emerges from this background is that policy planning is effective in managing the sustainability of specific aspects of tourism, but little is known about its potential effects on the sustainability of tourism in its entirety. For this reason, our purpose is to extend prior knowledge about policy planning by considering their impact on the overall sustainability of tourism flows.

Therefore, this paper evaluates policy interventions on the level of tourist flows prior to and after the enforcement of the laws to understand if and to what extent those intervention have been effective in managing the sustainability of tourist flows.

Drawing from this background we put forward three research hypotheses:

Hp1: The presence of a policy maker's intervention positively influence the sustainability of tourist flows.

Hp2: The degree of policy makers' intervention positively influence the sustainability of tourist flows.

Hp3: The presence of a management plan for the city with "tourism" identified as a key area moderates the relationship between the degree of policy makers' intervention and the sustainability of tourist flows.

2. RESEARCH DESIGN

To answer the research question, the research design is articulated in two parts: the first is dedicated to the measurement of the degree of policy makers' interventions; the second investigates the relation between the degree of policy makers' interventions and tourist flows.

2.1 Data and Sample

To run our analyses, we collected tourism-related information for the city of Florence in the time-period 2015-2022. Florence is one of the most popular tourist destinations in Italy and one of the most visited cultural sites in the world; located in the Tuscany region, the city has been on the UNESCO World Heritage List since December 1982. Due to the many museums and the Uffizi Gallery renowned for being the oldest art museum in modern Europe, there is the strongest concentration of works of art known in the world. The Uffizi Gallery recorded an attendance of EUR 2,362,000 visitors in 2019 (before the spread of Coronavirus pandemic) and it is one of the most visited museums in Europe (Statista, 2022) and the second in Italy for the highest income, EUR 35,648,000, after only the Colosseum in Rome.

Florence is the perfect context for our study since it is characterized by high levels of tourist flows which generate consequences in terms of overcrowding and unsustainability of tourism. Therefore, local authorities have been enacting regulations and recommendations to manage the level of tourist flows and to limit detrimental tourists' behaviors. The aim of this research is to analyze the content and the extent of those regulations to understand if they have been effective in managing the excessive level of tourism (Neuts and Nijkamp, 2012; Tokarchuk et al., 2020).

For the first part of the analysis, we collected policy planning documents enacted by the Municipality of Florence and the UNESCO office of Florence. The documents were directly provided by those offices and allowed us to form our database.

Subsequently, we collected data related to tourists flows, specifically data related to tourists' presences and arrivals, thanks to the collaboration of the UNESCO office of Florence. Those pieces of information have been collected monthly by the Municipality of Florence from 2015 to 2022.

2.2 The degree of policy makers' interventions

To assess if regulatory intervention have been effective for the management of tourist flows, the first part of our research will be conducted resorting to the manual content analysis technique. This technique is particularly effective for studying narrative information (Krippendorff, 2018) and therefore it fits well our need to measure the extent of policy makers' interventions (Job et al., 2017). The coding categories are:

1. a policy planning intervention exists, and it specifically refers to tourist flows management as a key area;
2. the policy planning intervention specifically reports the actions undertaken to manage tourist flows;
3. the policy planning intervention specifically provides methods to measure the effectiveness of the aforementioned actions.

Therefore, if no policy planning intervention exists, the degree of planning assumes a value of 0. As opposite, when a policy planning intervention exist, it may report more than one action undertaken to manage tourist flows; in that case, we attributed a score of 1 to each action undertaken. Finally, when the intervention also provides indication about how to measure the achieved results, we attributed an additional score of 1. We will finally resort to a measure of the degree of interventions that varies between 0 and 1 according to what illustrated above.

2.3 Empirical measures

Tourism_Flows_t is the dependent variable, and it is measured twofold by employing the monthly number of tourists arrivals or presences in Florence.

Regulation_{t,pres} is the independent variable of the first regression model; it is a dummy variable that indicates, for a certain year, the sole presence of a policy planning intervention. *Regulation_t* is the independent variable of the second model, measured as illustrated in the previous paragraph. *ManagementPlan* is a variable that captures, for a specific year, the presence of a

management plan for the city with “tourism” identified as a key area. *Regulation_t x ManagementPlan* is the moderator of the relation under investigation, and it aims at capturing the possible moderating role of the management plan in the main relation.

EU captures the percentage of tourists coming from the European Union. *GDP_t* is the gross domestic product in each of the origin country (Garin Munoz and Montero Martin, 2007). *Entry_Tax* is the income coming from the tourist tax aggregated at the monthly level. *Occu_Rate* is the occupancy rate of hotels in Florence as provided by Statista. The occupancy rate is a key metric used in the hotel industry. It is calculated by dividing the number of occupied rooms by the number of available rooms, in a specific period of time, and multiplying by 100 in order to obtain a percentage. *Aiport* is the annual number of passengers traveling through the Florence Peretola Airport. *Sale_Prop* is the average price for properties for sale in Florence.

2.4 Regression models

We will run an Ordinary Least Square (OLS) for the entire set of analyses. We will employ the following regression models:

$$(1) \text{Tourism_Flows}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Regulation}_t \text{pres} + \beta_2 \text{Entry_Tax} + \beta_3 \text{EU}_t + \beta_4 \text{GDP}_t + \beta_5 \text{OCCU_RATE}_t + \beta_6 \text{Airport}_t + \beta_7 \text{Sale_Prop}_t + \sum \beta_j \text{Year FE} + \varepsilon_t$$

$$(2) \text{Tourism_Flows}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Regulation}_t + \beta_2 \text{Entry_Tax} + \beta_3 \text{EU}_t + \beta_4 \text{GDP}_t + \beta_5 \text{OCCU_RATE}_t + \beta_6 \text{Airport}_t + \beta_7 \text{Sale_Prop}_t + \sum \beta_j \text{Year FE} + \varepsilon_t$$

$$(3) \text{Tourism_Flows}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Regulation}_t \text{x ManagementPlan} + \beta_2 \text{Entry_Tax} + \beta_3 \text{EU}_t + \beta_4 \text{GDP}_t + \beta_5 \text{OCCU_RATE}_t + \beta_6 \text{Airport}_t + \beta_7 \text{Sale_Prop}_t + \sum \beta_j \text{Year FE} + \varepsilon_t$$

The first model considers the sole presence of a policy planning intervention, while the second focuses on the degree of planning put in place to manage the sustainability of tourist

flows. The third and last model considers the presence of a management plan for the city as a moderator of the relation between the dependent and the independent variable.

3. EXPECTED RESULTS AND CONTRIBUTIONS

The level of tourist flows is rapidly becoming unbearable for some cities. To avoid arriving to a tipping point towards collapse, it is necessary to put in place mechanisms to ensure the development of sustainable strategies in tourism management (Job et al., 2017). Previous literature analyzed, between other, city planning as a strategy to face the excessive levels of tourist flows (Calle-Vaquero et al., 2021). Therefore, there is evidence that cities with developed tourism planning have superior conservation outcomes (Job et al., 2017).

The main purpose of this research is to understand if policy planning intervention are effective in managing the sustainability of tourist flows. Drawing from prior literature, we expect to find a positive relationship between the degree of policy intervention and the level of tourist flows (Calle-Vaquero et al., 2021; Job et al., 2016, 2017). Moreover, we expect the presence of a management plan for the city to be a moderator of the aforementioned relation due to the specific characteristics of this document. The latter, in fact, can be seen as a detailed report by the destination manager aimed at bringing out the main criticalities in site's management. These criticalities should be taken into consideration by policy makers to correctly address the issue.

In this sense, we aim at contributing to existing literature which focuses only to the analysis of management plan. Specifically, our analyses will be conducted on a wider range of policy intervention to assess the overall degree of planning.

Moreover, we aim at understanding if the degree of policy intervention is really affecting the sustainability of tourism flows or if a more specific regulation is needed to face the issue. In this sense, this research could offer a practical contribute to policy makers to revise

their strategy and focus on sustainability related aspects of tourism. Therefore, this work could have a big, innovative, impact in terms of the preservation of the city of Florence. In fact, as in many other cities in the world, city management is currently focused on building indicators that measure the sustainability of tourism. However, the retrospective measurement of the phenomenon allows to highlight the great topicality of the problem, but on the other hand it does not allow to identify actions and strategies to stem the problem upstream and prevent it from reaching the no-return point (Stoll-Kleemann and Job, 2008).

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